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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Using Auxiliary Mirrors for Improved Surface Coverage in Depth Scanning

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ABSTRACT Depth cameras have become an integral part of a wide range of applications, including industrial inspection, reverse engineering, human–robot collaboration, and biomechanical analysis. Their practical use, however, is limited by a narrow field of view and self-occlusions, which often prevent complete surface coverage of the scanned object. This paper introduces a methodology for systematically determining the optimal placement of a depth camera and an auxiliary planar mirror to maximize surface visibility. To this end, a simulation tool was developed that models camera rays, their reflections from the mirror, and their intersections with objects. The proposed method combines geometric visibility analysis with an optimization procedure that searches for configurations with maximum coverage. Validation was performed on a set of twenty objects ranging from simple geometric primitives to complex reference models. While a standalone camera achieved an average coverage of 51.68 %, the addition of a single planar mirror increased this value to 85.46 %, with complete coverage achieved for several objects. A complementary user study demonstrated that manually chosen configurations exhibit high variability and do not outperform the algorithmic design. The results confirm that the use of mirrors provides a cost-effective solution for overcoming occlusion-related limitations without resorting to multi-camera systems, and that the proposed methodology delivers consistent performance across diverse object geometries. The approach is particularly applicable in industrial inspection, robotic vision, and other domains where complete geometric information is essential.

INDEX TERMS Depth camera, occlusion, mirror, sensor placement, coverage optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Depth cameras are widely used for shape acquisition and object detection across many domains, including reverse engineering [1], quality inspection, sports biomechanics [2], virtual and augmented reality, autonomous vehicles, and robotics [3]. Depth cameras provide distance information for individual points in space relative to their local coordinate system. However, the practicality of these technologies is constrained by their limited field of view. A single camera

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can capture an object only from one side. For objects with complex geometries or when multiple objects are scanned simultaneously, self-occlusion occurs, leaving certain surface regions hidden from the camera’s perspective.

The impact of occlusion is evident in many real-world tasks. In robotic manipulation and collaborative applications, occlusions arise from the moving robot body, grippers, manipulated objects, human hands, and other critical components. Several authors have addressed occlusion detection. Nazareus et al. proposed a method based on a deep neural network trained to predict whether a given robot state is observable or occluded [4]. Sampaziotis et al. introduced a

computationally efficient method that leverages the URDF model of the robot to generate a virtual depth map. This map represents the robot's view from the camera perspective and allows identifying of which regions in the real image are actually occluded by the robot's body [5].

Occlusion can be addressed through various approaches, each with specific advantages and limitations. A straightforward strategy is multi-view acquisition using different camera positions, or the deployment of multiple cameras distributed around the object. However, such approaches increase hardware complexity and the difficulty of subsequent data fusion, particularly in real-time applications [6]. Oščádal et al. proposed a methodology for positioning depth cameras in collaborative applications to monitor potentially hazardous zones in human–robot cooperation [7].

Another strategy relies on algorithmic methods that do not directly remove occlusion but attempt to reconstruct and estimate the missing parts from partially available data. This group includes depth completion algorithms [8], instance segmentation under occlusion [9], pose estimation from partial views [10], and approaches based on shape priors and generative models [11].

An alternative and sensor-efficient solution is the use of mirrors, which extend the visual coverage of a single camera by reflecting object regions that would otherwise remain hidden. Several studies have demonstrated methods for reconstructing depth data from mirror reflections and confirmed that mirrors can significantly improve scene coverage. Akay et al. proposed a system with a single depth camera and planar mirrors, enabling the creation of virtual viewpoints and solving the calibration between real and virtual cameras [12]. Nguyen et al. presented a system using one time-of-flight depth camera and two planar mirrors to generate multiple viewpoints without adding extra sensors [13]. Yoshioka et al. designed a system combining a tilting depth camera with a planar mirror, where the tilt angle is adaptively adjusted to reveal occluded regions [14].

What these approaches lack, however, is a principled methodology for determining the placement of a depth camera and a mirror. Prior work focuses on how to use mirrors once they are already positioned, whereas this paper addresses the inverse problem: automatically identifying camera–mirror configurations that maximize surface visibility for objects of arbitrary shape. The novelty of this work lies in formulating this placement task as a general optimization problem and in providing a simulation-based solver capable of evaluating and comparing candidate configurations over the entire spatial domain.

This paper proposes such a methodology by introducing an iterative procedure for jointly determining the optimal camera and mirror placement to achieve maximum surface coverage. The approach integrates a geometric visibility simulation with a search over feasible camera and mirror poses, establishing a unified framework for mirror-assisted coverage optimization.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, a simulation application was designed in C++ with a visualization interface based on DirectX technology. The tool allows users to construct custom scenes and simulate the behavior of a stereo vision depth camera, planar mirrors, and scanned objects. Based on the simulation results, the percentage of surface coverage can be evaluated, and configurations that maximize it can be identified.

The following subsections provide the mathematical description of the key components implemented within the simulation framework.

A. DEPTH CAMERA AND MIRROR SIMULATION

In the simulation, the position and orientation of the camera in space are defined by a homogeneous transformation matrix

$$\mathbf{T}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_c & \mathbf{t}_c \\ \mathbf{0}^\top & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{R}_c denotes the camera orientation and \mathbf{t}_c specifies the camera position with respect to the global coordinate system \mathbf{T}_w .

To simulate sensing, user-defined parameters of the depth camera are defined – horizontal resolution W , vertical resolution H , horizontal field of view FOV_h , vertical field of view FOV_v , and maximum sensing range L .

The depth camera is mathematically modeled as a regular set of rays

$$\mathcal{R} = \{\mathbf{r}_i\}_{i=1}^{W \cdot H}, \quad (2)$$

where the number of rays corresponds to the number of pixels of the depth camera. In general, a ray is defined as

$$\mathbf{r}_i = \left(O_i, \ell_i, \hat{\mathbf{d}}_i \right), \quad (3)$$

where $O_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denotes the ray origin, $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the unit direction vector and $\ell_i \in [0, L]$ is the ray length. For rays originating from the camera, it holds that $\ell = L$, $O = \mathbf{t}_c$ and their direction vectors $\hat{\mathbf{d}}$ in the camera coordinate system are given as

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}}(u, v) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x_n^2 + y_n^2 + 1}} \begin{bmatrix} x_n \\ y_n \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $u \in \{0, \dots, W-1\}$ is representing the horizontal pixel index in the image, $v \in \{0, \dots, H-1\}$ is the vertical pixel index, and x_n a y_n are normalized image coordinates

$$x_n = \left(\frac{u}{W-1} - 0.5 \right) \cdot \tan \left(\frac{FOV_h}{2} \right), \quad (5)$$

$$y_n = \left(\frac{v}{H-1} - 0.5 \right) \cdot \tan \left(\frac{FOV_v}{2} \right). \quad (6)$$

The transformation of the direction vector $\hat{\mathbf{d}}$ into the world coordinate system \mathbf{T}_w is obtained using the rotation matrix

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}}_w = \mathbf{R}_c \cdot \hat{\mathbf{d}}. \quad (7)$$

A planar mirror in the simulation is represented as a rectangle in space. Its position with respect to the global coordinate system \mathbf{T}_w is expressed using the homogeneous transformation matrix

$$\mathbf{T}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_m & \mathbf{t}_m \\ \mathbf{0}^\top & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{R}_m = [x_m, y_m, z_m]$ is the rotation matrix that defines the orientation of the mirror. The columns of \mathbf{R}_m represent the orientation of the local mirror axes, with x_m indicating the mirror width direction, y_m the mirror height direction, and z_m the mirror normal vector. The vector \mathbf{t}_m specifies the position of the mirror center in the world coordinate system \mathbf{T}_w . The mirror is defined by its width w and height h , which determine a rectangle in its local coordinate system in the plane $z_m = 0$,

$$P_m(u, v) = \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad u \in \left[-\frac{w}{2}, \frac{w}{2}\right], \quad v \in \left[-\frac{h}{2}, \frac{h}{2}\right]. \quad (9)$$

For simplification of the subsequent computations, the rectangle representing the mirror is replaced by a pair of triangles, $\triangle(A, B, C)$ and $\triangle(A, C, D)$, which are defined by the corner points of the mirror

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{w}{2} \\ -\frac{h}{2} \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, & B &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{w}{2} \\ -\frac{h}{2} \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \\ C &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{w}{2} \\ \frac{h}{2} \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, & D &= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{w}{2} \\ \frac{h}{2} \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The mirror representation can be transformed into the world coordinate system as

$$P_w = \mathbf{T}_m \cdot P_m. \quad (11)$$

B. RAY CASTING IMPLEMENTATION

The simulated scene contains the sensed object, depth cameras, and mirrors. The object’s surface is represented by a set of triangles \mathcal{O} obtained from the STL model, while the mirrors are described by triangles \mathcal{M} . Together they form a unified set \mathcal{T} , which simplifies the subsequent ray-casting algorithm by providing a consistent representation for all scene elements.

$$\mathcal{T} = \mathcal{O} \cup \mathcal{M} = \{t_j\}_{j=1}^{N_{\mathcal{T}}}, \quad (12)$$

where each triangle t is defined by its vertices and a flag indicating whether the triangle belongs to the object or to the mirror

$$t_j = (V_{1j}, V_{2j}, V_{3j}, f_j), \quad f_j = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if object} \\ 1, & \text{if mirror.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The goal of the ray-casting algorithm is to detect object intersections by rays while accounting for possible ray reflections from mirrors. The algorithm performs the following steps independently for each ray $\mathbf{r}_i \in \mathcal{R}$.

First, back-facing triangles that cannot be intersected by the ray are filtered out. For each triangle $t_j \in \mathcal{T}$ the normal vector of triangle is computed as

$$\mathbf{n}_j = \frac{(V_{2j} - V_{1j}) \times (V_{3j} - V_{1j})}{\|(V_{2j} - V_{1j}) \times (V_{3j} - V_{1j})\|}. \quad (14)$$

A triangle t_j is relevant for the ray \mathbf{r}_i only if

$$\mathbf{n}_j \cdot \mathbf{d}_i < 0. \quad (15)$$

For all relevant triangles, intersections are computed using the Möller–Trumbore algorithm [15]. This yields a set of intersections

$$\mathcal{Q} = \{q_k\}_{k=1}^{N_{\mathcal{Q}}}, \quad (16)$$

where each intersection q_k is defined by the intersection point P_k , the distance from the ray origin s_k , the triangle type f_k , and the normal vector of the intersected triangle \mathbf{n}_k

$$q_k = (P_k, s_k, f_k, \mathbf{n}_k). \quad (17)$$

Subsequently, the closest intersection between the ray and the triangles is determined as

$$q_k^* = \arg \min_{s_k}. \quad (18)$$

The intersection q_k^* is valid if its distance from the ray origin does not exceed the ray length ($s_k \leq \ell_i$). If the closest intersection q_k^* belongs to an object triangle ($f_k^* = 0$), the intersection is stored in the set of ray–object intersections \mathcal{P} , and the computation terminates. However, if the closest intersection belongs to a mirror triangle ($f_k^* = 1$) a new reflected ray is generated as

$$r' = (P_k^*, \mathbf{d}'_i, \ell_i - s_k^*), \quad (19)$$

where the origin is the intersection point P_k^* , the length equals the remaining distance of the original ray after the reflection point, and the direction vector is computed from the original direction \mathbf{d}_i and the mirror normal \mathbf{n}_k^* as

$$\mathbf{d}'_i = \mathbf{d}_i - 2(\mathbf{d}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_k^*) \cdot \mathbf{n}_k^*. \quad (20)$$

The entire procedure is then recursively repeated with the new ray r' until the ray intersects the object, no further intersections are found, or the remaining ray length is exhausted.

C. COVERAGE SIMULATION

In order to objectively evaluate the suitability of the placement of the depth camera and mirror, it is necessary to quantify how much of the object’s surface is actually captured by the depth camera. The following section therefore describes an algorithm for estimating the percentage coverage of the object based on a geometric visibility simulation.

In accordance with equation (12) the object in the simulation scene is represented by a set of triangles \mathcal{O} read from an STL file.

Since the individual triangles of the object may vary significantly in size, it is not feasible to evaluate surface coverage solely by the ratio of covered to uncovered triangles. For this reason, the object triangles are uniformly sampled with a set of discrete points \mathcal{S} using the algorithm proposed in [16].

$$\mathcal{S} = \left\{ S_i \in \mathbb{R}^3 \right\}_{i=1}^{N_S} \quad (21)$$

These points S_i represent test locations on the object surface that are checked for coverage by the camera rays. The distribution of sampling points across the surface is controlled by two user-defined parameters. The first specifies the spacing, i.e., the distance between points and their rows when placed on the triangle surfaces. The second is the voxel size, applied during subsequent voxelization to suppress excessive point density, particularly in the vicinity of triangle vertices.

From the previous simulation, we obtain the set of ray-object intersections

$$\mathcal{P} = \left\{ P_j \in \mathbb{R}^3 \right\}_{j=1}^{N_P} \quad (22)$$

A user-defined detection radius $\rho > 0$ is introduced, which specifies that each intersection point “covers” its surrounding neighborhood within this radius, as illustrated in Figure 1. A point $S_i \in \mathcal{S}$ is considered covered by the camera if there exists an intersection $P_j \in \mathcal{P}$ such that

$$\|S_i - P_j\| \leq \rho. \quad (23)$$

FIGURE 1. Schematic illustration of the coverage criterion for object surface points. Each camera ray intersection P_j (red dot) with the object surface is associated with a detection radius ρ (green-filled circle with dashed outline). Surface points (black dots) are considered covered (lime dots) if they lie within the radius ρ of at least one intersection.

The set of covered points \mathcal{S}' is defined. Each point S_i may be covered by multiple intersections, but it is included in \mathcal{S}'

only once.

$$\mathcal{S}' = \{S_i \in \mathcal{S} | \exists P_j \in \mathcal{P} : \|S_i - P_j\| \leq \rho\} \quad (24)$$

The overall object coverage by the camera can then be expressed as the ratio

$$c = \frac{|\mathcal{S}'|}{|\mathcal{S}|} \in [0, 1]. \quad (25)$$

D. CAMERA AND MIRROR POSITION SOLVER

This section describes the procedure for determining the optimal positions of the camera and the mirror. The proposed methodology is based on the assumption that the measurement accuracy of points in real stereo vision sensing depends on the distance between the object and the camera. Points captured through mirror reflections behave as if they were located at a greater distance, which in the simulation is represented by the extended path length of the ray from the camera to the object. Consequently, data obtained via the mirror exhibit lower accuracy. For this reason, the proposed procedure first optimizes the camera position and only then the mirror position. Although joint optimization of both components could result in a slightly higher overall coverage, the chosen approach prioritizes higher measurement accuracy over maximum coverage.

To determine the positions, a solver is introduced that operates on a set of candidate camera and mirror placements in space (e.g., defined as a regular grid covering the region around the object)

$$\mathcal{G} = \left\{ G_i \in \mathbb{R}^3 \right\}_{i=1}^{N_G} \quad (26)$$

The object center is denoted as $C_o \in \mathbb{R}^3$. The coverage from a candidate position G_i is denoted as $c(G_i)$ in accordance with equation (25).

First, the optimal position for a standalone camera without a mirror is determined as follows. For each position $G_i \in \mathcal{G}$, the camera is placed at $(\mathbf{t}_c = G_i)$ such that its z_c axis points toward the object center.

$$z_c = \frac{C_o - G_i}{\|C_o - G_i\|} \quad (27)$$

The camera’s rotational orientation around this axis is then set so that the x_c axis lies in the horizontal plane of the global coordinate system, thereby eliminating tilt relative to the horizon. For all possible positions, ray-casting is simulated and the corresponding camera coverage $c(G_i)$ is computed. The position with the maximum coverage is then selected as

$$G_c^* = \arg \max_{G_i \in \mathcal{G}} c(G_i). \quad (28)$$

In the next stage of computation, the camera is fixed at position G_c^* , and a complementary mirror is sought such that it lies within the camera’s field of view. To this end, the camera frustum is used to determine the subset of candidate positions visible to the camera

$$\mathcal{G}_{vis} \subseteq \mathcal{G}. \quad (29)$$

For each position $G_j \in \mathcal{G}_{vis}$, the mirror is placed at ($\mathbf{t}_m = G_j$) and its contribution to the overall coverage is evaluated. The mirror normal \mathbf{n}_m is determined for each placement such that a ray from the camera directed toward the mirror center G_m is reflected toward the object center C_o , see Figure 2.

$$\hat{\mathbf{n}}_m = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{mo} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{cm}}{\|\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{mo} - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{cm}\|} \quad (30)$$

FIGURE 2. Geometric configuration of the camera and mirror used in the coverage simulation. The camera is placed at G_c and oriented so that its z_c axis points toward the object center C_o . The mirror is placed at G_m and oriented such that a ray from the camera aimed at the mirror center is reflected toward the object center.

All remaining components of the mirror transformation matrix are then calculated, with $z_m = \hat{\mathbf{n}}_m$. The rotation about this axis is chosen so that the mirror’s x_m axis lies in the horizontal plane of the global coordinate system.

For all possible positions of the mirror \mathcal{G}_{vis} , ray casting is simulated and the total coverage of the camera $c(G_j)$ with the mirror located at point G_j is calculated. Then, the position that provides maximum coverage is selected as

$$G_m^* = \arg \max_{G_j \in \mathcal{G}_{vis}} c(G_j). \quad (31)$$

E. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY

The computational cost of evaluating a camera or camera–mirror configuration is dominated by the ray-casting step. Let $R = W \cdot H$ denote the number of rays generated by the depth camera, N_T the number of triangles of the object and mirror, and N_S the number of sampling points used in the coverage evaluation. For each configuration, every ray is tested for intersection with all relevant triangles, which yields a worst-case time complexity of

$$O(R \cdot N_T). \quad (32)$$

After ray casting, coverage is computed by associating sampling points with nearby ray–object intersections within the detection radius. A direct evaluation requires

$$O(N_S \cdot R), \quad (33)$$

although this component is typically smaller due to the uniform distribution of sampling points. The overall computational cost of a single configuration is therefore

$$O(R \cdot N_T + N_S \cdot R), \quad (34)$$

with the ray-casting term being dominant.

The solver first evaluates N_G candidate camera positions and then evaluates a subset of mirror positions $N_{G,vis}$ lying inside the camera frustum. The total computation required for the full search is thus

$$O(R \cdot (N_T + N_S) \cdot (N_G + N_{G,vis})) \quad (35)$$

This expression makes explicit that the total cost scales linearly with the camera resolution, the geometric complexity of the object, and the size of the camera and mirror search grids.

III. QUANTIFYING THE BENEFITS OF THE MIRROR

The following section describes an experiment aimed at quantitatively determining the extent to which object surface coverage can be increased when scanning with a single depth camera augmented by a planar mirror, compared to the baseline configuration using only one camera.

A. EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

In this experiment, the scanning of 20 objects, shown in Figure 3, was simulated using an Intel RealSense D435i depth camera. The dataset includes basic geometric primitives, more complex general shapes, real-world mechanical components, and two well-known reference models commonly used for validation purposes (the Stanford Bunny and the Newell

FIGURE 3. Object dataset used in the experiment for quantifying the benefits of the mirror.

teapot). The size of each object was limited so that all of them fit within a cube with an edge length of 500 mm.

For each object, the percentage of surface coverage was computed following the methodology described in Section II. The geometry of the search space for possible camera and mirror placements was defined by a cylindrical grid. The grid dimensions were determined by its inner radius, outer radius, and height. The discretization of candidate positions was specified by the number of samples in the radial, angular, and vertical directions. The parameters controlling the distribution of test points on the object surfaces and the detection radius ρ were determined empirically, corresponding to the distance between two intersections on a planar object produced by adjacent rays at varying camera–object distances. Higher sampling density improves the evaluation of fine surface details but increases computation time, while the detection radius must match the simulated camera resolution. Values of radius that are too small cause fragmented uncovered regions, whereas overly large values may incorrectly mark occluded areas as visible. The specific values of the simulation parameters used in the experiment are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Simulation parameters used in the experiment.

Parameter	Value
Grid	
Inner radius	0.3 m
Outer radius	1.7 m
Height	2 m
Number of radial samples	10
Number of angular samples	36
Number of height samples	10
Total number of positions	3600
Depth Camera	
Horizontal resolution [W]	640 px
Vertical resolution [H]	480 px
Horizontal field of view [FOV_h]	87°
Vertical field of view [FOV_v]	58°
Maximum ray length [L]	3 m
Mirror	
Width	0.5 m
Height	0.375 m
Coverage	
Point spacing	0.005 m
Voxel size	0.005 m
Detection radius [ρ]	0.01 m

For each object, coverage values were first computed for all camera positions within the grid. These values were then visualized in the form of a heat map, shown in Figure 4. Subsequently, for the best-performing camera position, coverage values were computed with the mirror placed at all grid positions lying within the camera frustum. These results were also visualized as a heat map, presented in Figure 5.

B. RESULTS

The simulation results clearly confirm the benefit of augmenting a single depth camera with a planar mirror.

FIGURE 4. Heat map of object coverage achieved by the camera. Color encodes the coverage level obtained from different candidate camera positions within the scanning workspace; light green indicates higher coverage, whereas red denotes lower coverage.

FIGURE 5. Heat map of the additional coverage contributed by the mirror at each candidate position. The map is computed with the camera fixed at its optimal placement; only positions within the camera frustum are evaluated. Light green denotes higher additional coverage, whereas red indicates lower coverage.

For all 20 tested objects, the percentage of surface coverage increased compared to the baseline configuration using only the camera (see Figure 6). On average, the standalone camera achieved 51.68 % coverage, whereas the addition

FIGURE 6. Graph of the percentage coverage of individual objects obtained with the standalone camera and with the extended field of view using the mirror.

of the mirror increased this value to 85.46 %, which represents average coverage improvement of 33.78 % (see Figure 7). The lowest improvement observed after adding the mirror was 26.20 %, specifically for object 12, while the highest improvement was 41.32 % for object 14. For two objects, specifically objects 4 and 14, complete coverage was achieved by adding a mirror.

FIGURE 7. Graph showing the coverage distribution of all tested objects when scanned with the camera alone and with the camera-mirror configuration.

As an extension of the algorithm, an additional verification was carried out to evaluate whether orienting the mirror according to the procedure described in Section II-D results in an optimal configuration. In this analysis, the mirror orientation was systematically rotated around the x_m and y_m axes relative to the baseline setting. The simulations showed only an average improvement of 0.3 %, achieved at the expense of considerably higher computational cost — while evaluation of n mirror positions on a grid requires n simulations, the inclusion of m distinct mirror orientations increases the number of simulations to $n \cdot m$.

To evaluate the computational feasibility of the proposed solver, we measured execution times for a representative subset of five objects. For each object, we recorded the triangle count of the STL model, the number of surface testing points, the number of evaluated mirror positions, and the runtime required to determine the optimal camera and mirror placements. All measurements were performed on a workstation equipped with an Intel Core i7-9700F CPU, 32 GB RAM, and a NVIDIA RTX 3080 Ti 12 GB VRAM GPU. The results summarized in Table 2 confirm that the runtime scales consistently with the computational complexity derived in Section II-E. Although the execution times are not negligible, they are acceptable because the method is intended for offline sensor-system design rather than real-time operation, and further reductions in runtime remain possible through code optimization or the use of acceleration structures.

TABLE 2. Computational statistics for five representative objects.

Object ID	Triangle count	Testing points	Mirror positions	Camera time [s]	Mirror time [s]
2	12	54 674	1 114	67.6	11.4
5	504	58 250	1 242	62.6	9.7
14	8 206	4 792	649	102.5	21.0
17	11 172	20 457	1 021	142.4	41.4
19	57 834	23 223	1 012	621.3	200.1

C. REAL-SCENE VERIFICATION AND COMPARISON WITH SIMULATION

To evaluate how well the simulation-based visibility model translates to real measurements, an additional experiment was conducted using a physical setup comprising a RealSense D435i depth camera, a planar mirror, and three representative objects (a sphere, a cube, and a robotic arm segment). For each object, a real point cloud was acquired while the scene contained both the object and the planar mirror. Points observed via the mirror were correctly transformed using the known pose of the mirror, allowing the mirrored and direct measurements to be merged into a single coherent point cloud. The same camera and mirror poses were then reproduced in the simulation environment. A virtual scene was constructed such that the camera to object and mirror to object transformations exactly matched those of the real experiment.

This provided, for each object, a pair of point clouds: one obtained from real measurements and one generated by the simulator under identical geometric conditions. Figure 8 illustrates the resulting real and simulated point clouds, together with photographs of the corresponding measurement setups. This paired dataset enables a direct comparison of observed and predicted visible surface regions and serves as a validation of the simulation-based visibility model.

FIGURE 8. Comparison of real and simulated point clouds for three representative objects. Left column: real depth measurements. Middle column: simulated visibility results for identical camera-mirror poses. Right column: real measurement setups.

A cross-object comparison shows that the simulated and real point clouds share the same overall structure and exhibit generally consistent visible regions, although the correspondence is not exact. The simulation correctly predicts which parts of the object become observable, but the real measurements display local irregularities in point density and surface completeness caused primarily by depth-sensor noise and by the fact that the simulation does not model the distance-dependent depth accuracy characteristic of stereo-vision cameras. Despite these deviations, the real and simulated point clouds follow the same visibility pattern, confirming that the simulation captures the essential geometric behavior of the system and is suitable for determining camera–mirror configurations.

IV. COMPARISON BETWEEN ALGORITHMIC AND MANUAL PLACEMENT OF CAMERA AND MIRROR

The placement of the camera and mirror is critical for achieving maximum coverage of the scanned object surface. The proposed algorithm determines these positions automatically through simulation-based optimization; however, in practice, it is necessary to precisely configure and replicate such arrangements in a real environment. This requirement imposes demands on the calibration equipment used as well as on the measurement and alignment procedures of the individual components with respect to the object.

The designed experiment compares the results obtained from algorithmic placement of the camera and mirror with those achieved by human-selected configurations. The objective of this comparison is to assess the extent to which the theoretically optimal solution derived from simulation corresponds to practical placement under real-world conditions, and to examine whether the human factor can, in some cases, achieve comparable or even superior coverage.

A. EXPERIMENT DESCRIPTION

The experiment involved 20 participants, comprising university staff and students. Participants were instructed to first position the camera and then the mirror according to their own judgment, with the objective of achieving the best possible coverage of the presented object. The experimental setup is shown in Figure 9.

During the placement of the camera and mirror, participants had access to a live stream from the camera, but they were not provided with real-time feedback on the actual surface coverage. Each participant was tasked with optimizing the coverage of three objects shown in Figure 10. At the beginning, participants were thoroughly briefed on all aspects of their involvement in the experiment. They were informed about the procedure for recording their proposed positions and the methodology used to evaluate object coverage during scanning. In addition, the key experimental conditions were explained, including camera parameters, its operating range, and the defined area within which the camera and mirror could be positioned.

FIGURE 9. Experimental stand for positioning the camera and mirror around the object during the experiment.

FIGURE 10. Objects sensed during the experiment (1 - Tank, 2 - Vice, 3 - Arm).

Verbal and written consent to participate was obtained from all participants. They were also informed that their participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw from the experiment at any time without any penalty. All participant data were anonymized, and only the proposed camera and mirror positions were recorded and stored.

Once the participant has positioned the camera as desired, the scanned object is temporarily removed from the scene and replaced with a calibration polyhedron with ArUco markers, which is then photographed. The camera's transformation relative to the scanned object is calculated from this image.

After saving the image of the polyhedron, the scanned object is returned. In the next step, the participant is tasked with placing a mirror. The transformation of the mirror relative to the camera is determined using a 3D gridboard. The proposed calibration aids are based on the publication [17]. The angles between the individual marks on this gridboard are determined based on several previous measurements described in [18]. The accuracy of position and orientation readings using this method reaches 0.025 rad and 0.7 mm at a distance of 600 mm. Once the participant is satisfied with the mirror placement, another image is taken from the camera and the mirror position is read. The participant proceeds in this manner for the next two objects.

The obtained camera and mirror positions are then transferred to the simulation environment. For simulation purposes, STL models of real components are created. Here, the individual levels of object coverage are calculated in the simulation using the camera and mirror positions proposed by the participants in the experiment. The simulation parameters are identical to those in Section III.

B. RESULTS

The results of the positions obtained from the participants in the experiment are compared with the positions proposed by the algorithm. The graph in Figure 11 shows that manual placement of the camera and mirror leads to high variability in the results, reflecting the subjective approach of individual participants and their ability to estimate the optimal position. Although in some cases human participants manage to achieve comparable values, no participant proposes a better position than the algorithm.

FIGURE 11. Comparison of the percentage coverage of objects with manual and algorithmic positioning.

The overall average of manual solutions remains below the level achieved by the algorithmic solution. The

TABLE 3. Percentage coverage of object surfaces.

	Tank	Vice	Arm
Camera			
Manual Placement (average)	54.65 %	52.90 %	45.22 %
Algorithm	58.20 %	63.91 %	48.58 %
Improvement	3.55 %	11.01 %	3.36 %
Camera + Mirror			
Manual Placement (average)	82.02 %	87.71 %	63.31 %
Algorithm	90.78 %	94.93 %	75.30 %
Improvement	8.77 %	7.22 %	11.99 %

individual coverage averages for manual and algorithmic position settings, including their differences, are shown in Table 3.

V. CONCLUSION

This study extends previously published approaches that use mirrors to expand the field of view of depth cameras and thus increase the coverage of the scanned scene. In particular, this study introduces a new general methodology for systematically determining the optimal position of the camera and mirror relative to objects of any shape, thus going beyond previous solutions focused on connecting depth cameras and mirrors in specific applications. The developed simulation tool provides an accurate calculation of coverage based on geometric visibility analysis and also creates a basis for objective comparison of different camera and mirror arrangements.

The position design methodology is tested on twenty objects of various shapes. On average, the system was able to propose a camera position with 51.68 % object coverage. With the mirror involved, the average coverage increased to 85.46 %. In some cases, complete coverage of the object surface is achieved. These measurements demonstrate that the proposed methodology is capable of designing suitable camera and mirror positions across a variety of object shapes.

Although the paper demonstrates the method using a single camera and a single mirror, the underlying simulation framework and optimization procedure are directly applicable to configurations with multiple mirrors and multiple reflections. The ray-casting model naturally supports additional reflections without modification, as each reflection is treated as a new ray with an updated origin, direction, and remaining path length.

In practice, however, depth reconstruction based on multi-bounce reflections presents several challenges. Each reflection increases the effective optical path length, which reduces measurement accuracy in stereo-vision systems whose depth uncertainty grows with distance. Furthermore, even small errors in the estimated pose of the mirror propagate directly into the reflected ray direction, and these errors accumulate when multiple reflections are involved. As a result, while the method generalizes naturally at the simulation level, real-world deployment of multi-mirror or multi-reflection setups is significantly more sensitive to calibration accuracy and depth-sensor limitations.

Another important aspect is the comparison with manual configuration design. The results of the experiment show that some participants were able to design camera and mirror positions that provided coverage close to the algorithmic solution. However, the high variability of results across participants proves that systematic optimization based on simulation provides consistently better results than human estimation, even in the case of complex objects.

The simulation confirms that the integration of flat mirrors can be an effective means of overcoming the problem of self-shading of the field of view of depth cameras without the need for complex multi-camera systems. In terms of applications, the methodology offers a cost-effective solution for industrial inspection, reverse engineering, and robotic applications where the availability of complete geometric data is essential. Typical use cases include robot workspace and human–robot collaborative workspace monitoring, scanning of mechanical components, inspection of aesthetic surface defects on visible parts and automated assembly verification.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Haleem, M. Javaid, R. P. Singh, S. Rab, R. Suman, L. Kumar, and I. H. Khan, “Exploring the potential of 3D scanning in Industry 4.0: An overview,” *Int. J. Cognit. Comput. Eng.*, vol. 3, pp. 161–171, Jun. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666307422000171>
- [2] K. Maciejewski, F. Martins, D. Martinho, M. Sliž, H. Sarmento, É. R. Gouveia, and K. Przednowek, “Advancing sport biomechanics with depth cameras: Systematic review of current applications and future directions,” *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Sport*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 148–169, Jun. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://sciendo.com/es/article/10.2478/ijcss-2025-0009>
- [3] V. Tadic, A. Toth, Z. Vizvari, M. Klincsik, Z. Sari, P. Sarcevic, J. Sarosi, and I. Biro, “Perspectives of RealSense and ZED depth sensors for robotic vision applications,” *Machines*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 183, Mar. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2075-1702/10/3/183>
- [4] J. Nazareus, S. Reichhuber, M. Amersdorfer, L. Elsner, R. Koch, S. Tomforde, and H. S. Abbas, “Learning occlusions in robotic systems: How to prevent robots from hiding themselves,” in *Proc. 16th Int. Conf. Agents Artif. Intell.*, pp. 482–492, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.scitepress.org/Link.aspx?doi=10.5220/0012431000003636>
- [5] S. Sampaziotis, S. Antonakoudis, M. Kiatos, F. Dimeas, and Z. Douglari, “A lightweight method for detecting dynamic target occlusions by the robot body,” 2023, *arXiv:2302.06890*.
- [6] P. Ošádal, T. Spurný, T. Kot, S. Grushko, J. Suder, D. Heczko, P. Novák, and Z. Bobovský, “Distributed camera subsystem for obstacle detection,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 12, p. 4588, Jun. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/22/12/4588>
- [7] P. Ošádal, T. Kot, T. Spurný, J. Suder, M. Vocetka, L. Dobeš, and Z. Bobovský, “Camera arrangement optimization for workspace monitoring in human–robot collaboration,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 1, p. 295, Dec. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/23/1/295>
- [8] Y. Zhang and T. Funkhouser, “Deep depth completion of a single RGB-D image,” in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit.*, Jun. 2018, pp. 175–185. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8578124/>
- [9] R. Wu and P. Yang, “An RGB-D vision-guided robotic depalletizing system for irregular camshafts with transformer-based instance segmentation and flexible magnetic gripper,” *Actuators*, vol. 14, no. 8, p. 370, Jul. 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0825/14/8/370>
- [10] T. Hodan, D. Baráth, and J. Matas, “EPOS: Estimating 6D pose of objects with symmetries,” in *Proc. CVPR*, Jun. 2020, pp. 11700–11709. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9157391/>
- [11] J. Zeng, C. Bao, R. Chen, Z. Dong, G. Zhang, H. Bao, and Z. Cui, “Mirror-NeRF: Learning neural radiance fields for mirrors with whitted-style ray tracing,” in *Proc. 31st ACM Int. Conf. Multimedia*, Oct. 2023, pp. 4606–4615.
- [12] A. Akay and Y. S. Akgul, “3D reconstruction with mirrors and RGB-D cameras,” in *Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Vis. Theory Appl. (VISAPP)*, vol. 3, Jan. 2014, pp. 325–334. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7295101>
- [13] T.-N. Nguyen, H.-H. Huynh, and J. Meunier, “3D reconstruction with time-of-flight depth camera and multiple mirrors,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 38106–38114, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8408783>
- [14] K. Yoshioka, H. Okuni, T. T. Ta, and A. Sai, “Through the looking glass: Diminishing occlusions in robot vision systems with mirror reflections,” in *Proc. IEEE/RSJ Int. Conf. Intell. Robots Syst. (IROS)*, Sep. 2021, pp. 1578–1584. [Online]. Available: <https://keio.elsevierpure.com/en/publications/through-the-looking-glass-diminishing-occlusions-in-robot-vision->
- [15] T. Möller and B. Trumbore, “Fast, minimum storage ray-triangle intersection,” *J. Graph. Tools*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 21–28, Jan. 1997, doi: [10.1080/10867651.1997.10487468](https://doi.org/10.1080/10867651.1997.10487468).
- [16] T. Kot, Z. Bobovský, D. Heczko, A. Vysocký, I. Virgala, and E. Prada, “Using virtual scanning to find optimal configuration of a 3D scanner turntable for scanning of mechanical parts,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 16, p. 5343, Aug. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/21/16/5343>
- [17] P. Ošádal, D. Heczko, A. Vysocký, J. Mlotek, P. Novák, I. Virgala, M. Sukop, and Z. Bobovský, “Improved pose estimation of aruco tags using a novel 3D placement strategy,” *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 17, p. 4825, Aug. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1424-8220/20/17/4825>
- [18] J. Maslowski, J. Chlebek, and Z. Bobovský, “Improving position estimation of 3D gridboard with ArUco markers in robotic multi-camera systems,” in *Proc. Advances Service Industrial Robotics*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2025, pp. 533–540.

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